

IMPACT OF FERTIGATION LEVELS ON GROWTH AND YIELD OF HYBRID TOMATO

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Abstract

An experiment was carried out to study the effect of fertigation levels on growth and yield of hybrid tomato production at Instructional Farm of Department of Irrigation and Drainage Engineering, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola. during the rabi season of 2024-25. The experiment was laid out in Randomized Block Design (RBD) with five treatments which include four drip fertigation levels (120%, 100%, 80% and 60% of RDF) and control treatment of traditional fertilization at 100% RDF. These all treatments are replicated four times. Growth and yield of tomato was found maximum (838.67q/ha) in treatment T1 (120% RDF) and that was also resulted in highest water use efficiency as 2.83q/ha-mm.

Keywords: fertigation, drip, tomato, RDF, WUE

Introduction

Agriculture is a major economic contributor, representing 14% of the GDP and about 11% of exports. India possesses the world's largest gross irrigated area and is the biggest consumer of groundwater. The nation's average annual rainfall is 1200 mm. Projections indicates India's population will hit 1.6 billion by 2050, escalating the country's demands for food, water and energy. Consequently, India is likely to confront acute water scarcity by 2050.

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) is a prominent solanaceous vegetable crop extensively cultivated in India, holding a prime position among vegetables. It is a high valued crop consumed both fresh in salads and cooked in curries. Known globally as the 'love apple', 'golden apple' or 'poor man's apple', tomato has achieved significant worldwide importance. It is a rich source of vitamins A and C, as well as potassium. The red colour is due to lycopene pigment, which acts as a potent antioxidant for reducing damage from free radicals (Ayyar, 2019). Major tomato-producing states in India include Andhra Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Karnataka, Gujarat, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Odisha, and West Bengal.

In the year 2024–25, tomato cultivation in India covered an area of 853.27 thousand hectares, producing 25,959.43 thousand tonnes with a productivity of 27.7 tonnes per hectare, indicating improved yield levels despite a slight decline in cultivated area. During the same year in Maharashtra, tomato was grown over 56.47 thousand hectares, with a production of 1,512.37 thousand tonnes and a productivity of 26.2 tonnes per hectare, reflecting better performance in terms of output and efficiency compared to earlier years.

India ranks as the third largest producer and consumer of fertilizers globally. However, the nutrient consumption per hectare and fertilizer use efficiency remain notably low within the country. The primary reasons for this low efficiency include the types of fertilizers used and the application methods typically adopted by Indian farmers. Consequently, there is a clear necessity to develop an appropriate fertilizer application method that can enhance both the quantity and quality of crop yields. Fertigation is the technique of applying water-soluble solid fertilizers or liquid fertilizers directly through a drip

irrigation system. In fertigation, nutrients are delivered directly into the wetted soil volume beneath the emitter, where root activity is most concentrated (Ayyar, 2019).

Drip fertigation combined with mulching stands as one of the most effective management strategies, capable of significantly improving water management practices. The benefits of mulching in vegetable crop production are well-established. Mulch is essentially a protective layer of material spread over the soil surface. It enriches and safeguards the soil while creating a more favorable growing environment. Simultaneously, it acts as a barrier to moisture loss from the soil. Mulches can efficiently reduce water vapour loss, soil erosion, weed proliferation, and nutrient leaching. Mulching mitigates soil deterioration, curtails weed infestation, provides a beneficial microclimate for root development, and inhibits water evaporation. The plastic materials commonly used for mulching are polyvinyl chloride or polyethylene films, with polyethylene being the preferred choice for crop production.

Material and Methods

A study was conducted during rabi season of 2024-25 to examine the effects of different fertigation levels on hybrid tomato production at instructional farm of Department of Irrigation and Drainage Engineering, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola.

Climate at experimental site

Akola is geographically situated between North latitudes 20°16' and 21°17', and East longitudes 76°38' and 77°38'. Akola station receives an average annual rainfall 819 mm. The climate of Akola is subtropical semi-arid, featuring three distinct seasons: a hot and dry summer from March to May, a warm and rainy monsoon from June to October, and a mild, cold winter from November to February. The average minimum temperature recorded is 12.6°C, while the mean maximum temperature reaches 42.4°C.

Details of experimentation

The experiment was laid out in Randomized Block Design (RBD) with five treatments which include four drip fertigation levels and control treatment of which details are as given in following table 1.

Table 1. Treatment details

Treatments	Specification
T ₁	Drip fertigation with 120% of RDF
T ₂	Drip fertigation with 100% of RDF
T ₃	Drip fertigation with 80% of RDF
T ₄	Drip fertigation with 60% of RDF
T ₅	Conventional application of fertilizer with 100% RDF (Soil application of basal dose of 50% N + 100% P + 100% K through solid fertilizers at the time of transplanting and remaining 50% N in twelve equal splits at an interval of ten days)- Control

Tomato seedlings (Syngenta Saaho) were transplanted in a double row with spacing of 90 cm x 60 cm on ridge.

Irrigation and Fertigation Management

Prior to transplanting, a common irrigation was provided across all plots to bring the soil to field capacity. Accounting for the use of polyethylene mulch, which conserves approximately 20% of irrigation

water (Deshmukh, 2015), the water requirement for the tomato crop under drip was estimated at 80% of crop evapotranspiration (ETc). It was calculated using modified Penman- Monteith model, which is expressed as:

$$ET_0 = \frac{0.408 \Delta (R_n - G) + \gamma \frac{900}{T + 273} u_2 (e_s - e_a)}{\Delta + \gamma (1 + 0.34 u_2)}$$

where,

- ET₀ : Reference evapotranspiration, mmday⁻¹
 R_n : Net radiation at the crop surface, MJm⁻²day⁻¹
 G : Soil heat flux density, MJm⁻²day⁻¹
 T : Air temperature at 2m height, °C
 U₂ : Wind speed at 2 m height, m s⁻¹
 E_s : Saturation vapour pressure, kPa
 e_a : Actual vapour pressure, kPa
 Δ : Slope vapour pressure curve, kPa°C⁻¹
 γ : Psychrometric constant, kPa°C⁻¹

The values of crop coefficient used for different growth stages of tomato crop are referred from FAO 56. The crop evapotranspiration values for tomato crop is calculated by using following formula.

$$ET_c = K_c \times ET_0$$

where,

$$ET_c = \text{crop evapotranspiration (mmd}^{-1}\text{)}$$

$$K_c = \text{crop coefficient (dimensionless)}$$

$$ET_0 = \text{reference crop evapotranspiration (mmd}^{-1}\text{)}$$

Irrigation and Fertigation scheduling

To achieve optimal and efficient production, irrigation for the tomato crop was scheduled every day.

Table 2. Water requirement of tomato

Stage	Particulars	Total water applied (0.8 ETc), mm
I	Initial	25.23
II	Development	94.68
III	Mid	143.95
IV	Late	32.33
Total water applied, mm		296.19

It is cleared that maximum irrigation water was required during mid stage followed by development, late stage while minimum irrigation water was required during initial stage.

Table 3. Development of tomato crop

Sr. No.	Particulars	No. of branches				
		T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
1	30 DAT	4	4	3	2	3
2	60 DAT	7	6	5	4	6
3	90 DAT	9	8	7	6	8
4	120 DAT	11	10	8	7	9
Average		8	7	6	5	7
F Test		Sig.				
SE		0.2				
CD @5%		0.61				
Cv		6.27				

Table 4. Height of tomato plant

Sr. No.	Particulars	Height of Plant(cm)				
		T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
1	30 DAT	70	60	50	40	50
2	60 DAT	110	100	90	80	100
3	90 DAT	160	150	130	120	140
4	120 DAT	190	180	170	150	170

The recommended fertilizer dose of 300:150:150 N:P:K kg/ha was considered. In treatments T1 to T4, water soluble fertilizers (source – 19:19:19 WSF complex and urea) through drip fertigation was applied in 12 equal splits at an interval of 10 days. In control treatment T5, soil application of basal dose of 50% N +100% P + 100% K (sources – Urea and 19:19:19 WSF complex) were given as conventional fertilization through drip fertigation at the time of transplanting and remaining 50% of N (source-Urea) was given through drip fertigation.

Growth and yield parameters

Height of plant and number of branches were observed at every 30 days.

The first harvesting is done after the sixty days of transplanting when the fruits were fully developed and turned yellow to reddish colour. Further pickings were done at an interval of ten days. The yield of tomato from net plot in every treatment was observed in every picking. The total yield of the fruit harvested from net plot was recorded by cumulating yield per picking and expressed in kg per plot and then it is converted into quintal per hectare.

Water Use Efficiency

Using total yield recorded and irrigation water applied, water use efficiency was calculated using following relationship.

$$WUE = \frac{\text{Total Tomato production, q/ha}}{\text{Total irrigation water applied, mm}}$$

Results and Discussion

Water requirement of tomato

Irrigation equal to 80% ETc was provided daily. The stage wise irrigation water applied is as given in table 2.

Biometric observations

No of branches and height of plant were observed at every 30 days and same are presented in table and table 3 and 4, respectively.

	F Test	Sig.
	SE	1.8
	CD @5%	5.4
	Cv	3.1

Height of tomato plant was observed maximum in treatment T1 followed by T2 and T3. Height of tomato plant in treatment T3 and T5 was observed at par each other on 30, 60, 90 and 120 DAT. Height of

tomato plant was found minimum in treatment T4.

The number of flowers bears by plant and converted into fruits were also observed.

Table 5. Conversion of flowers into fruit

Sr. No.	Particulars	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
1	No. of flower	144	132	126	119	130
2	Fruits	142	129	123	114	127
3	Conversion Percentage	98.61	97.73	97.62	95.80	97.69

In all treatment conversion of flowers in to fruits was found more than 95%.

Yield of tomato during each picking was cumulated to obtain total yield of tomato. Total yield of tomato and water applied was used to estimate water use efficiency and presented in Table 6.

Water Use Efficiency

Table 6. Water Use Efficiency for hybrid tomato production.

Sr. No.	Particulars	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
1	Total yield, q/ha	838.67	781.34	722.53	656.31	747.74
2	Water applied, ha-mm	296.19	296.19	296.19	296.19	296.19
	Water use efficiency	2.83	2.64	2.44	2.22	2.52

The water use efficiency was observed highest for treatment T1 followed by T2, T5, T3 and T4. The minimum water use efficiency was found minimum for treatment T4.

Inference

It is suggested to implement treatment T1 (120% RDF with 12 equal splits of RDF at interval of 10 days) for maximum water use efficiency.

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